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ABSTRACT

WP3 of the EOM4SOIL project aims at evaluating the multiple effects of repeated External Organic Matter (EOM) application on soil health. Task 3.1 contributes to it by establishing a stocktaking of Medium to Long-Term Experiments (M/LTEs) studying the effects of EOM application on soils. Missing M/LTE data are filled by additional soil measurements on Short-Term Experiments (STE), lead by Task 3.2. Ultimate goal of the WP3 (Task 3.3) is to perform a multicriteria assessment using relevant M/LTE data in order to compare the effects of EOM application under different pedo-climatic conditions.

This report presents the result of the Task 3.1. First, an exhaustive meta-database of European M/LTEs studying the effects of EOM application on soil health (D3.1.1) has been set up from available online data sources. Subsequently, in order to provide data analysts with M/LTE data, a detailed list of necessary information (D3.1.2) was compiled to establish a concise selection of relevant M/LTEs (D3.1.3). This short-list was reinforced by collecting metadata directly from the trial manager.

Online research allowed to list more than 200 European M/LTEs. Two groups of data analysts implied in the EOM4SOIL project shared the type of data they are looking for, which permits to select 26 relevant M/LTEs.

Consequently, the inventory of EOM-M/LTEs enables the gathering and comparison of experiments based on different pedo-climatic contexts, types of EOM applied, and monitored soils, crops, and EOM properties. Furthermore, this study highlights the gaps in long-term scientific research on EOM, including issues related to the representativeness of soil types, studied EOMs, and monitored soil properties. Additionally, the process of collecting metadata reflects the availability of information on European M/LTEs online, emphasizing the importance of implementing best practices for sharing M/LTE metadata, particularly concerning monitored soil, crop, and EOM properties.

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	5
List of Tables.....	5
List of Annexes.....	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1. Context.....	6
1.2. General approach.....	6
2. List of medium- to long-term experiments on EOM application (D3.1.1).....	8
2.1. Materials and methods.....	8
2.1.1. Available online database.....	8
2.1.2. Selection criteria.....	9
2.1.3. Completing metadata with available maps.....	10
2.1.4. Data Analysis.....	10
2.2. Description of the database.....	12
2.2.1. Available metadata.....	12
2.2.2. Types of EOM.....	13
2.2.3. Properties measured on EOM.....	14
2.2.4. Share by countries.....	15
2.2.5. Share by crop type.....	15
2.2.6. Starting dates.....	15
2.2.7. Share by soil type.....	16
2.2.8. Soil properties.....	17
2.2.9. Crop properties.....	18
2.3. Discussion.....	19
2.3.1. Data quality: current issues.....	19
2.3.2. Perspectives.....	20
3. List of the necessary data (D3.1.2).....	21
3.1. Meetings with EOM4SOIL WP leaders to identify M/LTE data users and data needs.....	21
3.2. Listing and collecting supplementary metadata.....	22
4. Harmonized database for a selection of M/LTEs (D3.1.3).....	23
5. References.....	25

List of Figures

Figure 1. Outline of the tasks developed in WP3 – T.3.1 of the EOM4SOIL project: “List of medium/Long Term Experiments and measured elements database”.....	7
Figure 2. Location of the 201 M/LTEs dealing with application of EOM to soil on the map of Europe. In green, M/LTEs for which a contact with the owner was established within the EOM4SOIL project for the consolidation of metadata (D3.1.3).	12
Figure 3. Count of M/LTEs by EOM type (in grey), including farmyard manure, slurry, compost, sewage sludge, organic amendments, biowaste, digestate, green waste, biochar and industrial sludge. The mentions of green manure and plant residues (in green) in the definition of treatments were also plotted.....	13
Figure 4. Count of M/LTEs by characteristics measured on external organic matter (EOM) applied to soil. CEC is cations exchange capacity. PCB is polychlorinated biphenyls. PAH is polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.....	14
Figure 5. Count of M/LTEs dealing with the application of EOM in Europe sorted by European country (a) and by starting year (b). The legend refers to the count of M/LTEs by crop type, with arable crops in yellow, fruit trees in rose and grassland in green.	15
Figure 6. Krona chart of the two first levels of the WRB classification extracted from the European Soil Database based on spatial location of the M/LTEs. The inner circle corresponds to major soil classes and the outer circle to the first qualifier.	16
Figure 7. Count of M/LTEs by occurrence of soil properties measured, sorted by chemical (yellow), physical (blue) and biological (orange) properties.....	17
Figure 8. Count of M/LTEs by occurrence of soil properties measured. Pests relates to weeds, pests and diseases.	18

List of Tables

Table 1. Overview of availability and reliability of general metadata of long-term experiments encoded in the database of EJP SOIL 7.3, the three publicly available Bonares resources and the GLTEN portal.	9
Table 2. List of metadata collected from the managers of the 26 selected M/LTEs.....	23

List of Annexes

Annex I. Table gathering encoded soil properties by categories.	26
Annex II. Table gathering encoded crop properties by categories.	27
Annex III. List of EOM M/LTEs and available metadata (D3.1.1). Excel file attached to this report. ...	28
Annex IV. List of the necessary data (D3.1.2). Excel file attached to this report.	28
Annex V. Harmonized consolidated database for a selection of M/LTEs (D3.1.3). Excel file attached to this report.....	28

List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
M/LTE	Medium to Long-Term Experiment
STM	Short-Term Experiment
EOM	External Organic Matter

1. Introduction

1.1.Context

The aim of the WP3 of the EOM4SOIL project (“External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health) is to study the multiple effects of repeated External Organic Matter application on soils. Task 3.1 consists in making a stocktaking of the Medium to Long-Term Experiments (M/LTEs) on repeated application of EOM (e.g. farmyard manure, slurry, sewage sludge, anaerobic digestate, compost, animal by products) carried out in Europe and to develop a consolidated database on these M/LTEs. Task 3.2 aims at filling missing data in the M/LTE database by performing additional measurements in Short-Term Experiments (STMs). Task 3.3 aims at performing a multicriteria assessment using M/LTE data in order to compare the services and disservices provided by different EOMs under different pedo-climatic conditions. The database provided by WP3 will feed into the meta- and multi-criteria analyses as well as the model projections in WP4-6.

This document focusses on Task 3.1, whose specific objectives are to:

- **OB1.1: Development of trans-European network of EOM Medium/Long Term Trials.** Among the project partner to determine and characterise EOM M/LTEs,
- **OB1.2: Development of a consolidated database of EOM M/LTEs.** Collect data (available and new) and compile them in a consolidated database adapted to the needs of WP6.

Therefore, the main goal of T3.1 is to establish a list of M/LTEs dealing with the application of EOM in Europe, in order (i) to provide a stocktaking and a map of M/LTE dealing with EOM application at European scale and (ii) to feed the EOM4SOIL project with data to analyse the long-term effects of EOM application on the properties of soil and the overall performance of agricultural systems.

Task 3.1 comprises three individual deliverables, annexed to this document:

- **D3.1.1** – the list of M/LTEs dealing with EOM application at European scale (**Annex III**);
- **D3.1.2** – the list of necessary data for data provision and analysis by EOM4SOIL partners (**Annex IV**); and
- **D3.1.3** – a harmonized database containing relevant metadata on a short-list of M/LTEs dealing with EOM application (**Annex V**).

For the sake of clarity, the three deliverables are presented altogether in the present report.

1.2.General approach

The general approach of the work developed in T3.1 to provide the three deliverable is summarized in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**

The D3.1.1 provides in a list as exhaustive as possible of existing M/LTEs at European scale. To realise this deliverable, the prelist of about 20 M/LTEs established by EOM4SOIL partners was extended to 201 M/LTEs, using multiple online resources. The database was completed with the best available and online metadata.

The D3.1.2 lists the necessary data (D3.1.2) for M/LTEs data users within the scope of the EOM4SOIL project. Therefore, M/LTEs data users were identified by individual meetings with WP leaders of the EOM4SOIL project, and the data necessary to meet their objectives were listed.

Based on the list of M/LTEs and of necessary data, metadata were harmonized and consolidated for a short-list of 26 M/LTEs, and finally compiled in the D3.1.3. For that purpose, direct contacts have been established with the M/LTE owner.

The ultimate goal of T3.1 is to feed T3.3 (multicriteria analysis of the effects of EOM application on soil properties) and T6.1 (modelling of multicriteria performance of EOM use) of the EOM4SOIL project.

Figure 1. Outline of the tasks developed in WP3 – T.3.1 of the EOM4SOIL project: “List of medium/Long Term Experiments and measured elements database”.

2. List of medium- to long-term experiments on EOM application (D3.1.1)

2.1. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Available online database

A pre-list of about 20 M/LTEs was established by EOM4SOIL partners and was available as a basis for the work. This pre-list was extended thanks to several existing online resources:

- Within the WP7.3 of EJP SOIL, a stocktaking of European M/LTEs is currently in progress. The project aims at “*harmonizing and improving previous/existing initiatives by creating an online database in which the metadata of ongoing European M/LTEs are gathered. This M/LTE database will be open access and will serve as a match-making platform between researchers and M/LTE managers*” (Blanchy *et al.*, 2020). The spreadsheet gathers general metadata on the M/LTE and a link to an individual file describing several aspects of the trial (general information, treatments, associated publications, soil type and advanced information on the phytotechnical itineraries of the M/LTEs including tillage, crop rotation, soil amendments, irrigation, pest and weed control and available data on soil and crops). The database currently counts 492 describing sheets of M/LTEs but the work is still in progress. Unfortunately, only a few trials are encoded in an exhaustive way. Most M/LTEs were completed with general information on the trial (name, location, contact person, associated scientific publications). The other fields of information are completed for some trials only (soil type, crop rotation, fertilizers, soil and crop measurements). According to our objective, the weakness of this database is the poor definition of the goal and design of the experiments, which complicates the selection of relevant M/LTEs. Furthermore, the database mainly gathers trials from countries represented within the EJP SOIL project. As a result, some countries are not represented (e.g. Ukraine, Belarus, Romania, Greece, Germany, Portugal ...). When completed, the description of the phytotechnical itineraries is very accurate for the last five years of cultivation but the start and end dates are not mentioned.

- The BonaRes portal is the second source of information on M/LTEs in Europe (**Erreur ! Référence non valide pour un signet.** compares the quality of available metadata for the three BonaRes resources, the GLTEN and the database developed in task 7.3 of the EJP SOIL project.

Table 1): “*BonaRes is short for Soil as a sustainable resource for the bioeconomy. In this funding initiative of the German Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) the focus is on the sustainable use of soils as a limited resource. The ultimate goal of BonaRes is to extend the scientific understanding of soil ecosystems and to improve the productivity of soils and other soil functions while developing new strategies for a sustainable use and management of soils. The BonaRes Portal provides information about the BonaRes projects, access to data, knowledge and models, as well as to decision support options for a sustainable soil management.*” Three resources are available through BonaRes, with contrasting levels of available metadata (**Erreur ! Référence non valide pour un signet.** compares the quality of available metadata for the three BonaRes resources, the GLTEN and the database developed in task 7.3 of the EJP SOIL project.

Table 1). Two databases originate from a collaboration between BonaRes and EJP SOIL whereas the third one includes data from six different networks (including EJP SOIL):

- First, 218 M/LTEs completed and validated through the WP7.3 of EJP SOIL were published on one BonaRes repository (<https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-jwhj-z839>; Blanchy *et al.*, 2020). One open access Excel file gathers all the information from individual M/LTEs.

- A second resource includes “616 M/LTEs from 30 different countries across Europe with a minimum duration of typically 20 years, including clustered information of the European M/LTEs in different categories (management operations, land use, duration, status, etc.). It consists of the updated version of the dataset published by Grosse *et al.* (2020) but is extended by further M/LTEs metadata, categories and research themes within a collaboration of BonaRes and EJP SOIL”. The data is also open access and can be downloaded as a .txt, .csv or .xls file via the following link <https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-40kc-2661> (Dönmez *et al.*, 2022).
- The third resource is an interactive overview map (<https://lte.bonares.de/>; “BonaRes”, n.d.) containing “information about 498 agricultural experiments with a duration of at least 20 years. The following networks are included: EJP SOIL (European Joint Programme), GLTEN (Global long-term experiment network), ILTER (International long-term ecological research), IOSDV (International Organic Nitrogen Fertilisation Experiment), NLFT (National Long-term Fertilisation Trials, Hungary) and RetiBio 2 (Italy).

- A last online database was explored for relevant M/LTEs related to EOM application to soil: The GLTEN metadata portal (<https://www.glten.org/>; “GLTEN”, n.d.) listing 291 trials around the world. “The GLTEN is a network of long-term agricultural experiments and associated researchers spanning six continents and representing a range of climates, environments, crop systems and farming practices”. GLTEN provides the best description of the trials but many relevant trials are lacking.

Erreur ! Référence non valide pour un signet. compares the quality of available metadata for the three BonaRes resources, the GLTEN and the database developed in task 7.3 of the EJP SOIL project.

Table 1. Overview of availability and reliability of general metadata of long-term experiments encoded in the database of EJP SOIL 7.3, the three publicly available Bonares resources and the GLTEN portal.

	EJP SOIL 7.3 (n=492)	Bonares Repository (EJP SOIL 7.3) (n=218)	Bonares overview map (n=498)	EJP SOIL – BONARES collaboration (n=616)	GLTEN (n=291)
	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dAGspPf0N0TxAoQAVkb00U8EQoD_LK50lp5mZ9tw3Hg/eLit#gid=0	https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-jwhj-z839	https://tools.bonares.de/lte/	https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-40kc-2661	https://glten.org/
Contact	very good	good	none	none	very good
M/LTEs description	good	poor	good	very good	very good
Soil type	good	none	very good	poor	very good
M/LTEs period	none	none	very good	very good	good
Climate	good	very good	none	none	very good

2.1.2. Selection criteria

We defined several criteria to select relevant trials in online databases. About the duration of experiments considered as “medium to long term”, experiments lasting or aimed to last for > 5 years

were considered. This includes i) ongoing experiments started > 5 years ago; ii) experiments that came to an end but lasted for > 5 years; and iii) ongoing experiments that lasted for < 5 years but aimed to last for > 5 years. To identify relevant M/LTEs on the topic of EOM application, we explored the different databases with key words related to organic fertilisation (organic fertilisation, manure, slurry, sludge, compost, digestate, (bio)waste, ...) in the description of the trial and of its treatments. In order to extract a maximum of relevant information from the different databases (having each of them strengths and weaknesses) and to avoid double-counting of M/LTEs, the correspondence between the different databases for one M/LTE was checked based on i) the trial location; ii) the name of the trial; and iii) start and end dates of the trial. If at least two out of the three factors were the same (e.g. same name and same trial location), the M/LTE was considered to be the same one in the two databases. The M/LTE was then characterized with a maximum of available information, keeping the most accurate one when one variable (e.g. soil type) appeared in more than one database.

2.1.3. Completing metadata with available maps

The database was completed by extracting values of World Reference Base (WRB) soil classes and textural characteristics from the European Soil Database v2.0 (ESDB, 2004), accessible online after registration on the website of the European Soil Data Center (“ESDAC”, n.d.). WRB main group and first qualifier were extracted automatically with ArcGIS Pro (Esri, 2023) from the polygons of the European Soil Database based on spatial location of the M/LTEs.

2.1.4. Data Analysis

Data were analysed with R4.1.2 (R Core Team, 2021), particularly with the ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), dplyr (Wickham *et al.*, 2023) and tidyr (Wickham *et al.*, 2023) packages. Most variables of interest in the dataset are text variables, with several of them freely encoded by the M/LTE descriptors (e.g. EOM type, soil and crop properties monitored, etc.). Analysis of the dataset mainly consisted in the description of the collected variables based on counts of recurrent characteristics (e.g. keywords, years, soil classes) for the different variables. To this end, a preliminary classification of the raw data was necessary for some variables.

2.1.4.1. EOM types

The definition of EOM types refers either to the feedstock (e.g. green waste), to the transformation process (e.g. digestate, compost, biochar) or to the origin of EOM (e.g. industrial or sewage sludge), alone or in combination (e.g. composted farmyard manure, green waste compost, hardwood biochar). Recurrent keywords used to characterise EOM were identified and used as EOM classes, with one new column created for each class of EOM. They include i) farmyard manure, ii) slurry, iii) compost, iv) sewage sludge, v) organic amendments, vi) biowaste, vii) digestate, viii) green waste, ix) biochar and x) industrial sludge. When one EOM was defined by a combination of characteristics (e.g. green waste compost), the two columns were ticked. If several EOM of a same type were used in one single trial (e.g. wood biochar and green waste biochar) the column “biochar” was ticked twice. The restitution of crop residues and the use of green manure are also frequently mentioned in the definition of EOM types. Whereas these organic inputs do not strictly respond to the definition of EOM, they are often used in combination with EOM in the definition of M/LTEs treatments on the topic of soil organic matter management. Therefore, the occurrence of crop residue restitution and green manure was analysed jointly with EOM types.

2.1.4.2. Soil and crop properties

To analyse soil and crop properties quantitatively, an initial step of cleaning was necessary to correct typos and spelling mistakes. All terms occurring in the “soil indicators” column were then automatically detected and listed by using R functions. Terms referring to the same concept (e.g. mycorrhiza vs arbuscular mycorrhiza, carbonates vs CaCO_3 , salinity vs electrical conductivity, etc.) were standardized. In total, 190 keywords remained for soil properties and 126 for crop properties. The last step consisted in classifying each term in an adequate category. Soil properties were split into physical, chemical and biological properties. Within these main classes, subcategories were created. Physical properties were divided into i) texture, ii) erodibility, iii) water dynamics and porosity and iv) soil temperature. Chemical properties were divided into i) cation exchange capacity, ii) acidity and salinity, iii) organic matter, iv) major nutrients (NPK), v) secondary major nutrients (Ca, Mg, Na, S), vi) metallic trace elements and vii) organic contaminants. Biological properties were divided into i) fauna, ii) microbial abundance, iii) microbial diversity, iv) microbial activity, v) N dynamics and vi) other biological properties (too inaccurate to be classified). Keywords associated to each category are provided in Annex I. For crop indicators, keywords were split into five classes: i) yield indicators, ii) crop quality, iii) crop growth, iv) crop contamination and v) pests (weeds and diseases). Keywords associated to each class are provided in Annex II.

2.2. Description of the database

The list (Annex III, D3.1.1) contains 201 M/LTEs dealing with the application of EOM to soil, mapped on Figure 2, with the environmental zones of the European territory (Metzger, 2005) in background, using the latest relative dataset (Metzger, 2018). On the map, a distinction is made between M/LTEs for which contact has been established with the manager(s) and those for which it has not (Figure 2).

2.2.1. Available metadata

For each M/LTEs, the following metadata are available: the name of the trial, the starting and ending dates, the description of the trial, the institution owning the M/LTE, the location of the trial, the environmental zone according to Metzger classification (Metzger, 2005), the type of crop (arable crop, fruit trees or grassland), the two first levels of the WRB classification extracted from the European Soil Database and the presence of the trial in the online resources from BONARES, EJP SOIL and GLTEN. Other metadata are available for a majority of M/LTEs: the type of EOM applied to soil (n=170), information on crop rotation (n=158), the area of the trial (n=139), an indication on soil texture (n=120), crop indicators (n=117), soil indicators (n=114), the contact person (n=110), the email of the contact person (n=101) and one more scientific article describing the trial (n=101).

Supplementary metadata available for a minority of M/LTEs includes : the URL to an official website (n=100), soil type (n=95), mean annual temperature (n=92) mean annual rainfall (n=91), information on the rate of application of EOM (n=88), elevation (n=86), the phone number of the contact person (n=34), the availability of the detailed phytotechnical itinerary (n=32) and information on EOM properties (n=24).

Figure 2. Location of the 201 M/LTEs dealing with application of EOM to soil on the map of Europe. In green, M/LTEs for which a contact with the owner was established within the EOM4SOIL project for the consolidation of metadata (D3.1.3).

2.2.2. Types of EOM

The shares of keywords associated to the definition of EOM types are presented in Figure 3. Among keywords related to EOM feedstocks, the highest occurrence is found for livestock manure, including farmyard manure (n=118) and slurry (n=44). Then come sewage sludges (n=23), biowaste (n=12), green waste (n=11) and industrial sludges (n=3). Among the keywords related to transformation processes, compost (n=45) comes first, followed by digestates (n=10) and biochars (n=9). Compost may relate to composted farmyard manure, green waste-, bio-waste- or sewage sludges compost. The raw materials composing digestates or biochars are also sometimes specified. The mentions of crop residues (n=21) and green manure (n=20) is also frequent in association with EOM *sensus stricto*.

Figure 3. Count of M/LTEs by EOM type (in grey), including farmyard manure, slurry, compost, sewage sludge, organic amendments, biowaste, digestate, green waste, biochar and industrial sludge. The mentions of green manure and plant residues (in green) in the definition of treatments were also plotted.

2.2.3. Properties measured on EOM

Information on the properties measured to characterize EOM was collected for 24 M/LTEs out of the 26 for which metadata were consolidated (see 0, D3.1.3). The occurrence of EOM properties for these 24 M/LTEs was plotted on **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**. The primary focus is the total content of N, measured in each of the 24 M/LTEs. For a majority of M/LTEs, total organic matter content, dry matter content, pH and total P and K contents are also measured. Other major nutrients (Mg, Ca, S), electrical conductivity (n=8) and trace metallic elements (n=11) are less frequently measured. The organic contaminants polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB, n=2) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH, n=3) are measured in EOM for a few M/LTEs only.

Figure 4. Count of M/LTEs by characteristics measured on external organic matter (EOM) applied to soil. CEC is cations exchange capacity. PCB is polychlorinated biphenyls. PAH is polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.

2.2.4. Share by countries

The consortium of EJP SOIL counts institutions from 24 European countries, with 20 countries out of the 27 countries of the European Union (Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden) and four other European countries (Norway, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom). In the list of M/LTEs dealing with the application of EOM (Figure 5a), 22 countries were represented (Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK). Three countries of the consortium (Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia) had no reference in the list, and only one country out of the consortium (Belarus) had references in the list. On Figure 5a, a notable fact is that Germany stands far beyond other European countries, with more than 70 M/LTEs identified. Far behind Germany, fourteen and eleven M/LTEs were found in Italy and United Kingdom, respectively. We identified between five and 10 M/LTEs for several countries (Austria, Belgium, Cech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Hungary, The Netherlands, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland) and less than five for the remaining countries (Belarus, Finland, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Slovenia and Turkey).

Figure 5. Count of M/LTEs dealing with the application of EOM in Europe sorted by European country (a) and by starting year (b). The legend refers to the count of M/LTEs by crop type, with arable crops in yellow, fruit trees in rose and grassland in green.

2.2.5. Share by crop type

A large majority of M/LTEs are cultivated with arable crops (n=172), whereas a significant number are cultivated as grasslands (n=20) or with fruit trees (n=9).

2.2.6. Starting dates

Figure 5b presents the number of M/LTEs that started in ten years periods dating from 1843. Only a small number of M/LTEs listed here started in the first half of the 20th century, with one to four new M/LTEs set up by decade until the 50s. This number increased largely in the second half of the 20th century until the beginning of the 21st century, with up to 31 M/LTEs set up by decade. The share of M/LTEs affected with grassland and fruit trees tended to increase from the 80s (Figure 5b).

2.2.7. Share by soil type

Unsurprisingly given the locations of the M/LTEs, Cambisols and Luvisols, dominant in the center of Western Europe, are the most represented soil types in our dataset (Figure 6). Podzols and Albeluvisols (Retisols in the last version of the WRB), subservient to more northern regions, have a smaller share, similarly to Phaeozems and Chernozems mainly located in continental plains of Eastern Europe. Fluvisols and Histosols also appear as significantly represented soil classes in the M/LTEs list. Nevertheless, the extraction of WRB soil map values based on M/LTEs location also identified M/LTEs in artificialized areas (Town), which underlines the limit of the approach. Analysis of the first level of qualifiers indicates a gradient of soil acidity from (slightly) acidic (Dystric) to alkaline (Calcaric), which underlines the diversity of soil conditions at this scale of work.

Figure 6. Krona chart of the two first levels of the WRB classification extracted from the European Soil Database based on spatial location of the M/LTEs. The inner circle corresponds to major soil classes and the outer circle to the first qualifier.

2.2.8. Soil properties

The occurrence of soil properties measured at M/LTEs are presented on Figure 7, sorted by chemical physical and biological properties. Among the three categories, chemical properties are the most commonly monitored. Soil organic matter comes first, followed by plant-available macronutrients (N, P, K and Ca, Mg and S) and indicators related to soil acidity and salinity. Trace metallic elements are also frequently monitored, unlike organic contaminants that receive little attention. Among physical properties, indicators related to water dynamics and porosity come first, followed by texture analysis, erodibility indicators and soil temperature, respectively. Among biological properties, indicators of microbial activity and abundance have a similar share, followed by N dynamics, fauna and microbial diversity indicators.

Figure 7. Count of M/LTEs by occurrence of soil properties measured, sorted by chemical (yellow), physical (blue) and biological (orange) properties.

2.2.9. Crop properties

Among the 117 M/LTEs mentioning a monitoring of crop properties, most of them measure yield- or biomass-related indicators. Indicators of crop quality are also mentioned frequently. Indicators related to crop growth, pests (weeds and diseases) and plant contamination were also identified, with a much lesser frequency.

Figure 8. Count of M/LTEs by occurrence of soil properties measured. Pests relates to weeds, pests and diseases.

2.3. Discussion

2.3.1. Data quality: current issues

Despite the significant number of M/LTEs identified on the topic of repeated EOM application to soil at European scale, the overall quality of the database remains quite poor for some variables. This is mainly due to i) the poor definition of the needs or of the instructions to fill out the form, or the poor respect of instructions by the encoder; ii) the lack of harmonization between databases used as sources for this stocktake; and iii) the incomplete character of the stocktake, tainted by clear geographical biases. In this section, we discuss these issues and propose ways of improvement.

2.3.1.1. *Missing data*

The incomplete and unbalanced character of this stocktake is clear. The best evidence is the plot of M/LTEs by countries (Figure 5a), highlighting the large dominance of German trials in the dataset. The relatively large size of Germany at the scale of European countries and its leading position in agricultural and soil science research may not entirely explain such an imbalance with the other countries. A bias certainly originates from the fact that the main sources of data used in this work are related to BONARES, a German soil initiative. Accordingly, we expect a high level of completeness for German M/LTEs compared to other European countries. The belonging to the EJP SOIL program appears as another important filter to understand the geographical biases in the stocktake, since out of the 21 countries for which M/LTEs were identified in the list, only one is not part of the EJP SOIL consortium (Belarus, with 1 M/LTE). Among participating countries, only three (Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia) are not represented. This may originate from a lack of representative from the concerned countries to complete initial tasks of stocktake that occurred during the first phase of the EJP SOIL program. Identifying the relevant contact persons for European countries not represented in the stocktake would be a path for filling the current the gaps.

The representation of a country in the stocktake doesn't guarantee the completeness of the data. To illustrate the idea that some relevant trials may be missing within countries well represented in the stocktake, let's take the example of biochar M/LTEs. In our list, we identified eight M/LTEs dealing with biochar application, located in Austria (n=2), Denmark (n=1), Estonia (n=1), Hungary (n=1), Italy (n=2), and Spain (n=1). Recently, Marazza *et al.* (2022) created a network of Long-Term Experimental Platforms regarding biochar application to soil (LTEP-BIOCHAR). They listed 18 M/LTEs, including 16 European trials. Even though the age criteria to define M/LTEs to is shorter (≥ 3 years) than the one we use here (≥ 5 years), the LTEP-biochar network includes several supplementary trials relevant for our list. For example, the biochar trial in Merelbeke, Belgium (e.g. Sánchez-Monedero *et al.*, 2019), was set up in 2011 and doesn't appear in our list. The same is true for the Donndorf-Eckersdorf trial established in 2010 in Southern Germany (Cooper *et al.*, 2020), having two rates of biochar application, alone or in mixture with compost. These are two examples of M/LTEs relevant for our survey, located in countries well-represented in the BONARES repositories or in the EJP SOIL program which haven't been recorded in the source databases.

2.3.1.2. *The challenge of harmonization*

The second challenge for the quality of the dataset is harmonization of information. Information collected for some variables can either be poor, disharmonized or even discordant. A telling example is soil type. The level of completeness is about 50 % (100 out of 201) for this parameter. The data include a mix of entries from the World Reference Base (WRB) classification and from the United State Department of Agriculture (USDA) classification, with the main soil class mentioned along with zero to three qualifiers. Some typos and spelling mistakes remain in the list (e.g. Phaenzem), or soil classes

from classification systems that we do not know (Redoxisol, Rigolsoil). For the sake of harmonization, WRB soil classes were extracted from the European soil database based on spatial location of the trial. As a result, the level of correspondence between encoded and extracted data is poor. This is either due to i) the discordance in the classification system used, ii) the poor description of soil type by the encoder or iii) the poor spatial definition of the European soil database (1:1 000 000).

Another example of disharmonized information is the definition of the goals of the M/LTEs, partially documented in the description of the trial, with some relevant information in the column related to the decision rules for treatment definition. The description of the trial returns to very generic information (e.g. field experiment on biochar and compost), to the definition of the initial goal of the trial at its set up or to generic or redefined goals for M/LTEs lasting for a long period of time. These issues of data harmonization relate, in part at least, to the multiplicity of data sources. The different databases exploited here had different goals and encoding instructions, resulting in conflicting or disharmonized information for some variables. This issue is difficult to solve.

2.3.2. Perspectives

To fill the current gaps and missing data, we encourage M/LTEs managers on the topic of repeated EOM application to soil to complete or correct the current dataset to improve its quality. An editable version of the database is associated to this document¹, along with accurate guidelines to fill in the form. Edits may consist in correcting or improving the information for one trial already encoded in the current version of the database, or the registration of new trials relevant for the topic. A validated, not editable version of the database is also publicly available. The database, attached to this report (D3.1.1, **Annex III**) will be hosted online (Zenodo repository).

¹<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1SOVC6QAuv5PATHTiUKfbc1S1d3l00Bko/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=109859544889801807665&rtpof=true&sd=true>

3. List of the necessary data (D3.1.2)

The second goal was to list necessary data (D3.1.2) for M/LTEs data users within the scope of the EOM4SOIL project. Therefore, M/LTEs data users were identified by individual meetings with WP leaders of the EOM4SOIL project, and the data necessary to meet their objectives was listed.

3.1. Meetings with EOM4SOIL WP leaders to identify M/LTE data users and data needs

Individual meetings were organized with the different WP of EOM4SOIL to identify whether they need M/LTEs data or not for their respective work. Here we present a summary of these meetings regarding this objective.

WP1

WP1 aims at developing a harmonized database of EOM characteristics (carbon content, fertilizing value, contaminant load, ...) and at quantifying the amount produced at national scale for partner countries. Therefore, WP1 does not require M/LTE data.

WP2

WP2 focusses on three processing technologies (composting, anaerobic digestion and pyrolysis) to i) optimize the potential of C sequestration in soil of EOM and ii) decrease GHG emissions and nutrient losses during EOM processing. WP2 does not require M/LTE data.

WP3

WP3 focuses on the long-term effect on soil quality of repeated application of EOM to soil. Their main source of information will be M/LTE data. Two main tasks within the WP require M/LTE data:

- Subtask 3.2.1, which aims at completing M/LTE datasets with parameters currently missing or disharmonized between M/LTEs and of interest for the project (aggregate stability, total organic carbon, microbial biomass, enzymatic activities).
- Task 3.3, which aims at performing a multi-criteria evaluation of the effect of repeated applications of EOM on soil properties, based on M/LTE data. This task will require M/LTEs data as complete as possible for a selection of trials (about 5). The approach consists in the calculation of several soil and crop quality indices from the raw data, using linear scoring functions (Obriot *et al.*, 2016). The tool currently comprises seven indices, related to soil fertility, soil biodiversity, soil biological activities, soil physical properties, soil contamination, and crop productivity (Obriot *et al.*, 2016). A reflection about the possibility to create supplementary indices is currently in progress.

WP4

WP4 focuses on the C balance and GHG emissions from EOM. In particular, two objectives of this WP are (i) to provide insights into the effect of the application of various EOM on microbial carbon use efficiency in soil (T4.3) and ii) to calculate a GHG budget for different EOM from their processing to their application to soil (T4.4). Nevertheless, the study of GHG emissions from soil is very specific and requires time series with continuous measurements at a high frequency. We did not identify any relevant M/LTEs in the database that was not already considered by the WP4. WP4 will therefore put the focus on short-term experiments implemented with a specific design for the continuous measurement of GHG emissions.

WP5

WP5 deals with soil contamination by EOM application. The work includes a synthesis of current limitations of EOM use by contaminants (T5.1), a quantification of EOM organic contaminants and

plastics and the effect of processing on the contaminant load (T5.2, T5.3) and the ecotoxicity of EOM with or without processing (cf processes of WP2). By lack of time and resources, WP5 will not focus on M/LTEs data but rather on i) the collection of data on national regulations and regulated contaminants in EOM from the partner countries; and ii) the effect of processing (composting, anaerobic digestion and pyrolysis) on EOM contaminants.

WP6

WP6 aims at providing practical guidelines for an optimal use of EOM on soil, based on information provided by the other WP and a multicriteria evaluation of the performance of EOM by modelling (T6.1). To meet this goal, WP6 hopes to identify a small number of M/LTE (n=2-3) with very complete metadata, phytotechnical itineraries and available time series of data on e.g. soil organic carbon content, mineral N content, soil contaminants, etc.

To sum up, three main M/LTE data users were identified within EOM4SOIL from the individual meetings:

1. T3.2 Supplementary analyses of M/LTE soil properties (Roberta Pastorelli, CREA)
2. T3.3 Multicriteria analysis of EOM effects on soil (Laure Vieubl, INRAE)
3. T6.1 Multicriteria performance of EOM use (Florent Levavasseur, INRAE)

3.2. Listing and collecting supplementary metadata

To meet the multiple goals of the data users, the necessary (meta-)data was listed by individual meetings with partners from WP3 and WP6 (D3.1.2, **Annex IV**). This list includes information on i) soil management practices, ii) EOM characteristics, iii) soil properties, iv) crop yield and quality, v) climatic data, vi) leaching water quality and vii) greenhouse gas emissions. An indication on the relevance of each parameter in the seven classes for the three WP is provided, with four different levels (critical +++, important ++, not essential +, or useless -).

As a result, WP3 relies particularly on an accurate monitoring of soil and crop properties, with a secondary interest for most other indicators listed.

For WP6, the goal is to assess the performance of modelling tools for the simulation of SOC stocks, crop yield and N losses. Therefore, they ideally need detailed annual data of soil management practices, EOM properties, crop yield and quality (C and N content) and permanent soil properties such as granulometry and CaCO₃. They need time series of soil non-permanent characteristics such as pH, bulk density, C and N tot content, mineral N content, water content at wilting point and at field capacity, metallic trace element content and soil microbial biomass. They also need time series for N losses (NH₃, N₂O and NO₃⁻) and for meteorological conditions (daily min and max temperature, rainfall, Penman evapotranspiration potential, ...). Nevertheless, the number of modelled parameters will be adapted according to the availability of data.

4. Harmonized database for a selection of M/LTEs (D3.1.3)

The goal of subtask 3.1.3 is to consolidate the metadata for a selection of M/LTEs, to select the most relevant trials to perform a multicriteria analysis of the long-term effect of EOM application on soil properties (T3.3) or to model the long-term influence of EOM application on the multi-performance of agricultural systems (T6.1). To meet these objectives, the metadata of M/LTEs was consolidated according to the needs of T3.3 and T6.1 (D3.1.2) for a short list of 26 trials for which a contact with the M/LTE manager had been successfully established.

Metadata were consolidated in two steps. First, online databases were exhaustively explored to complete the database as accurately as possible. Then, a form with filling instructions was sent to M/LTE managers to collect missing necessary metadata identified in subtask 3.1.2. This was done by sharing a template with missing meta-data to M/LTE managers:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1SOVC6QAuv5PATHiUKfbc1S1d3l0OBKo/edit#gid=1094586424>.

Table 2 presents the metadata required from M/LTE managers.

Table 2. List of metadata collected from the managers of the 26 selected M/LTEs

Metadata	Description of what is required
Description	General description of the trial and main objectives.
Name	
Institution	
Contact	
Email	
Phone number	
Country	
Localisation	
Latitude	
Longitude	
Elevation	
Climate T (°C) annual mean	Average temperature over the test period
Climate Rain (mm) annual mean	Average annual rainfall over the test period
Environmental Zone (Metzger, 2009)	
Starting date	
End date or on going	
Soil (WRB-FAO system)	
Soil texture	Textural class USDA, granulometry fractions: %clay, %silt, %sand.
Trial area	Total area of the trial (= number of individual plot x plot area)
Crop rotation	Evolution of crop rotation across time. Usual and Latin names.
Availability of the detailed phytotechnical itinerary	Please just enter "yes/no" concerning the availability of this information.
Type of EOM	
EOM properties	Any available information about EOM quality.

	E.g. pH, dry matter, nutrients, C/N, contaminants ...
Decision rule for treatment definition	1) What was the logic behind the choice of rate and frequency of EOM applications? 2) Is this decision rule realistic compared to common uses of this type of EOM in agriculture? E.g.1. To optimize soil carbon sequestration within the legal limits of N fertilisation. E.g.2. To study the accumulation of contaminants over time.
Rate of application of EOMs	Total amount for one application (e.g. 4 T C/ha or 170 kg N/ha). If different for each treatment, please precise.
Frequency of EOM application	
Number of EOM applications over the duration of the trial	
Period of application of EOMs	At which time of the year the EOM is applied on the field. If single application (e.g. biochar), precise the year of application.
Weather indicators	Type of weather data available (proximity to the meteorological station, measured variables, measurement frequency)
Soil sampling depth	
Soil indicators	Soil properties measured (e.g.: pH, total organic carbon, total organic nitrogen, bioavailable phosphorus, aggregate stability, bulk density, microbial biomass, denitrifying rate...)
Crop indicators	Crop properties measured (e.g.: yield, harvest quality...)
Leachate measurements	Monitoring of leachates (e.g.: nitrate, dissolved organic carbon, dissolved P...)
GHG measure	
Contact established	
Link to Bonares overview map	
Official website/Scientific articles	
EJP SOIL 7.3 ID	
Link to metadata file from EJP SOIL 7.3	

The consolidated database for the short list of 26 M/LTEs is annexed to this report (D3.1.3, Annex V). This list will be used by T3.3 and T6.1 to select relevant M/LTEs to meet their objectives, according to the availability of data.

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Annex I. Table gathering encoded soil properties by categories.

Physical properties			Chemical properties							Biological properties				
Texture	Erodibility	Water dynamics and porosity	CEC	Acidity/ Salinity	Organic matter	Major nutrients (NPK)	Secondary major nutrients (Ca, Mg, Na, S)	Metallic trace elements	Organic contaminants	Fauna	Microbial abundance	Microbial diversity	Microbial activity	N dynamics
granulometry	aggregate stability (slake test)	water holding capacity	CEC	pH	C	Nmin	Mg	micronutrients	PAH	earthworms	arbuscular mycorrhiza	soil microbia community composition	enzyme activities	N-mineralisation potential
Soil temperature	aggregate stability	air permeability at different water potentials	adsorption complex	pH (KCl)	N	NH4+	K	metals	PCB	nematods	TBI	species diversity	microbial activity	N2O flux
soil temperature	rainfall simulation tests	water retention characteristics		pH (H2O)	Cmin	NO3-	Ca	total Cu	pharmaceuticals	fauna	microbial biomass	species richness	basal respiration	N-mineralisation
	aggregate water-stable aggregates	water retention		pH (CaCl2)	Ctot	macronutrients	Na	total Zn	dioxin	soil zoological parameters	microbial biomass C	Shannon index	CO2 flux	Others (inaccurate)
		water content		CaCO3	Corg	phytoavailable P	Stot	total B	furan	ditellata	microbial biomass N	Pilous evenness	CH4 flux	aboveground biomass
	structure	coefficient of permeability		active CaCO3	OM	extractable K	Smin	total Fe	organic contaminants	oligochaeta	molecular microbial biomass	functional diversity	enzyme activities (hydrogenase-glucosidase-alkaline)	belowground biomass
	Aggregate Mean Weight Diameter	gravimetric moisture content		EC	Ntot	extractable P	S	total Mn	herbicides	mesofauna	microbial biomass (FE)	DNA sequencing	phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA)	H2O flux
	Structure Stability Index	macroporosity			Norg	nutrient availability	extractable Mg	Co		Cu in earthworms	Gram positive bacteria	bacterial communities	glomalin-related soil proteins	microorganisms
	sediment loss	mesoporosity			C:N ratio	Double lactate extractable P	extractable Ca	Cu			Gram negative bacteria	archaeal communities	continuous EDDY Covariance tower	
		bulk density			humus content	Double lactate	extractable Na	Cr			Fungi-to-bacteria	fungal	microbial activity (C-ergosterol)	
		dry bulk density			humus quality	Olsen P	extractable cations	Ni			microbial abundance			
					SOM	P compounds		Hg			microbial biomass (N-fixing bacteria-Rhizobium MPN)		soil respiration	
					SOC	CAL-P		Zn					beta-glucosidase	
					active C	CAL-K		Cd					alkaline	
					soluble organic carbon	P		Pb					urease	
					hot-water extractable carbon (HWEC)	Ptot		B					neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFA)	
					Water-extractable Carbon/Water-soluble Carbon	water-extractable P		Mn					protease	
					Sand-sized fraction MAOM (size)	P Sorption Capacity		Mo					phosphatase	
					Fine fraction MAOM (silt + clay size)	P saturation		extractable Al					dehydrogenase	
					C content	P fractions (soil tests in spring and autumn)		extractable Fe						
					C storage	assimilable K		extractable Mn						
					N content	assimilable P		total trace elements						
					N storage	extractable P (in ammonium acetate lactate)		extractable trace elements						
					C compounds	extractable K (in ammonium acetate)		trace elements						
					N compounds	bicarbonate-extractable								
					labile C	extractable ammonium								
					labile N	plant available N								
					Dissolved organic carbon (DOC)									
					hot-water soluble C									
					Total Extractable Carbon (TEC)									
					Humic Carbon (HC)									
					organic matter composition									
					dissolved organic matter (DOM)									

Annex II. Table gathering encoded crop properties by categories.

Yield	Quality	Growth dynamics	Contamination	Pests
Yield	macroelements	Field emergence	Cu uptake in plants	diseases
Crop yield	microelements	start of vegetation	heavy metal content	pests
crop residues	nutrient uptake	stand density before harvest	trace element content	weeds
DM	grain N uptake	density	Cd	weed abundance
grain yield	mineral N	biomass growth		weed species richness
total biomass	nutrient content	inventory ratings		weed species diversity
residues biomass	production quality	soil penetration		weed soil cover presence
Thousand Grain Weight	Biomass Carbon	Plant emergence		
Main crop yield	OM	stand density before harvest		
net sugar yield	C	stages of development		
TM	N	ripeness		
yield parameters	P	root distribution		
dry matter yield	K	start of flowering		
sorghum grain and stalks production	Mg	stand density		
aboveground biomass	Ca			
roots	Na			
Grapes yield	S			
winter wheat yield	starch content			
maize yield	other nutrients			
grain yields trait	components			
hectolitre grain weight	quality			
plant height	Zn			
plant density	Cu			
plant biomass	Mn			
yield trait	Canopy Composition			
biomass	N deprivation			
fresh weight	P deprivation			
dry weight	K deprivation			
seed cotton yield	N removal			
fibre yield	medium stand height			
Fresh yield	total N content of sorghum grain and stalks			
raisin yield	cellulose			
Cut grass yield	hemicellulose			
co-product yield	crude protein content			
yield stability	mineral content in grains			
yield structure	H isotopes			
Harvest index	N-balance			
leaves area	total N			
specific leaves weight (SLW)	Nutrient performance indicators			
average fruit weight	plant quality traits			
trunk circumference	total plant tissue N			
pruned wood	Biomass Nitrogen			
	Biomass Phosphorus			
	macroelements of leaves			
	microelements of leaves			
	fibre quality analysis			
	residual analysis			
	grape quality			
	mineral composition			
	botanical composition			
	N content			
	chlorophyll content			
	earliness index			
	fruit pH			
	fruit acidity			
	refractometric dry residue (RSR)			
	consistency and blush of fruit			
	fruit concentration of macroelements			
	fruit concentration of microelements			

Annex III. *List of EOM M/LTEs and available metadata (D3.1.1). Excel file attached to this report.*

Annex IV. *List of the necessary data (D3.1.2). Excel file attached to this report.*

Annex V. *Harmonized consolidated database for a selection of M/LTEs (D3.1.3). Excel file attached to this report.*

